

The conformational behaviour of free D-glucose— at last

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Abstract

The conformational behavior of isolated D-glucose has been revealed in this work using Fourier transform microwave spectroscopy coupled with laser ablation of crystalline α and β glucopyranose samples. Four conformers of α -D-glucopyranose and three of β -D-glucopyranose have been unequivocally identified on the basis of the spectroscopic rotational parameters in conjunction with *ab initio* predictions. Stereoelectronic hyperconjugative factors, like those associated to anomeric or gauche effects, as well as the cooperative OH \cdots O chains extended along the entire molecule, are the main factors driving the conformational behavior. The most abundant conformers exhibit counter-clockwise arrangement (*cc*) of the network of intramolecular hydrogen bonds.

Introduction

D-Glucose (C₆H₁₂O₆, see Fig.1a) is one archetypical monosaccharide having a critical role in energy metabolism of many living organisms,¹ its residues being components of important polysaccharides, and representing the major building block for many carbohydrate systems.² Like other six-carbon monosaccharides, it may exist in either linear or cyclic, pyranose or furanose, forms.² In aqueous solution, NMR studies have shown that the pyranose form is the dominant one.^{2,3} The nucleophilic addition of the C₅ hydroxyl group to the aldehyde group generates a hemiacetal, possessing a chiral center C₁. The cyclization leads to the occurrence of two anomeric species, α and β , according to the position of the OH group (see Haworth diagram in Fig.1b). For the pyranose forms, the chair configuration ⁴C₁ (⁴C₁ refers to a chair configuration where the C₄ carbon is above the reference plane C₂C₃C₅O and C₁ carbon is found below it, as depicted in Fig.1c) is dominant, with all substituents but the C₁ hydroxyl group (which assumes an axial orientation in the α anomer) in equatorial orientation.

It is commonly believed that the α anomer is more stable than the β anomer due to the stereoelectronic anomeric effect.⁴ However, when D-glucose is dissolved in water, the α and β

anomers are present in a 40:60 ratio in the 4C_1 ring conformation. The observed abundance of the β anomer in water could only be explained by taking into consideration strong solvation effects, that overcome the preference for the α anomer.⁵ Moreover, the glucopyranose's hydroxymethyl group conformation must be considered in terms of three staggered conformers, designated G+, G- and T (see Fig.1d), associated to the C6-O6-C5-O5 torsional angle, which assumes values of *ca.* 60°, -60° or 180°, respectively. Experimental observations in both solid phase⁶ and solution³ display approximately equal populations of G+ and G- conformers, with an almost complete absence of the T conformer. This propensity in glucopyranosides to adopt gauche conformations is known as gauche effect,⁷ generally accepted as a solvent-dependent phenomenon.⁸ Finally, the structural analysis of D-glucose requires the consideration of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between adjacent OH groups. Plausible formation of hydrogen bond networks reinforces their stability due to hydrogen bond cooperativity effects.⁹ The orientation of the hydroxyl groups is relevant to distinguish between the different conformers of D-glucose. A subtle variation in hydroxyl orientation is thought to account for differences in chemical and physical properties of this biologically relevant biomolecule.^{1,2}

Although the discussion of all above factors goes back many years, a clear dissection of these factors in archetype representative D-glucose has not been possible. The experimental results obtained in condensed phases by NMR³ and vibrational spectroscopy,¹⁰ as well as the X-ray and neutron diffraction,⁶ seem to indicate that a subtle balance between intrinsic and environmental effects governs the conformational preferences of D-glucose. To separate these contributions is crucial to obtain data of the isolated glucose in the gas phase. This highlights the importance of generating glucose in isolated conditions free from the influence of environmental effects to determine its intrinsic conformational properties. This is also relevant to understand its biological activity and to rationalize the structure of more complex polysaccharides, cyclodextrines or glycoproteins.¹¹

Apart from the number of theoretical studies on D-glucofuranose,^{5,12} there are no structural studies of this benchmark molecule in the gas phase, free from solvent influence. Only one vibrational spectroscopic study of α -D-glucofuranose isolated in Ar matrix has been reported.¹³ The IR signatures were interpreted with the help of *ab initio* computations in terms of the predominance of the predicted three most stable conformers. No comparable work has been reported for β -D-glucose. Laser spectroscopy through UV-UV and IR-UV double-resonance techniques has contributed to the description of the conformations of some β -phenylglucofuranosides.¹⁴ These studies are limited to vibrational resolution and the structural conclusions are not transferable to D-glucose because of the electronic chromophore at the anomeric position. Hence, among the relevant chemical compounds whose structures have been determined, the structure of free D-glucose has remained unknown until now.

In the last years, it has become possible to explore the architecture of solid biomolecules in the gas phase through the development of techniques which combine laser ablation (LA) for transferring them into the gas phase with Fourier transform microwave (FTMW) spectroscopy in a molecular beam (MB).¹⁵ The structure of several natural amino acids,¹⁶ nucleic acid bases,¹⁷ dipeptides¹⁸ and neurotransmitters¹⁹ has been unveiled for the first time. The rotational spectrum is extremely sensitive to the molecular geometry, so conformers can be discerned as totally different species. The shape of drugs such as aspirin²⁰ paracetamol²¹ and nicotine²² has been also revealed. Recently, this experimental approach has been successfully extended to the monosaccharides D-ribose²³ and D-fructose.²⁴

In this work we have examined for the first time the gas phase structure of D-glucose using this LA-MB-FTMW experimental technique.¹⁵ The low-temperature environment of a supersonic expansion provides the ideal medium for preparing individual conformers of α - and β -D-glucofuranose in virtual isolation conditions ready to be interrogated by a short burst of microwave radiation. The Fourier transformation of the temporal profile of the emanating radiation yields rotational spectra of superb resolution and sensitivity. A comparison of

experimental spectroscopic constants with those predicted by high level *ab initio* computations enables us to conclusively identify four conformers for α -D-glucopyranose and three for β -D-glucopyranose. All factors contributing to stabilization of the observed species have been discussed. Details of the investigation are given in the next sections.

Methods

The rotational spectra of α - and β -D-glucose (m.p = 153 and 157° C, respectively) have been investigated using our LA-MB-FTMW spectrometer, the details of which are described elsewhere.¹⁵ Solid rods of commercial α - and β -D-glucose samples, were formed by pressing fine powders mixed with minimum quantities of a binder, which were ablated by using a Nd:YAG picoseconds laser (35 ps, 10 mJ/pulse). The desorbed products were seeded in Ne (stagnation pressure 15 bar) and expanded adiabatically to form a supersonic jet into a Fabry-Pérot resonator. The delay time between opening the pulsed valve and the laser trigger was adjusted to optimize the amount of neutrals in the supersonic expansion. A short microwave radiation pulse (0.3 ms) in the range 3 to 10 GHz was then applied to macroscopically polarize the vaporized molecules. The microwave transient free-induction decay associated with molecular relaxation was registered in the time domain and Fourier-transformed to the frequency domain. The pulsed molecular beam was introduced parallel to the axis of the Fabry-Pérot resonator so each observed transition appears as a Doppler doublet. The resonance frequency is determined by the arithmetic mean of the two Doppler components. The estimated accuracy of the frequency measurements is better than 3 kHz.

The identification of the observed species is based on the agreement between the experimental and theoretical values of spectroscopic constants.^{15a,16a} Thus, we considered the most-stable conformers of α - and β -D-glucopyranose obtained previously^{12,5} from *ab initio* methods, to predict²⁵ the rotational constants and the electric dipole moment components relevant for the analysis of the spectra. A summary of these calculations for α - and β -D-glucose

is given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. We have used the same notation described before^{12b} to label the different conformers. The standard letters α or β are used to describe the anomer type. The next symbols, describe the configuration of the hydroxymethyl group. The symbol in capital letters, G^+ , G^- or T , describe the torsion angle $O_6-C_6-C_5-O_5$ (see Figure 1d) of about 60° , -60° or 180° , respectively. The lower case symbol g^+ , g^- , or t , describe in the same way the torsion angle $H_6-O_6-C_6-C_5$ (see Figure 1d). These symbols are followed by a slash and the symbol cl or cc describing respectively the clockwise (cl) or counterclockwise (cc) arrangement of the cooperative network of intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Then, after the slash, the last symbol, g^+ , g^- or t , gives the value of the torsion angle $H_1-O_1-C_1-C_2$ that describes the orientation of the anomeric hydroxyl group hydrogen atom.

Results

Rotational Spectrum of α -D-glucopyranose

The microwave spectrum of α -D-glucopyranose was investigated in first place. Our spectroscopic searches were guided by the estimated values of rotational constants and dipole moment components for each of the six plausible conformers below 600 cm^{-1} shown in Table 1. All conformers are predicted as prolate asymmetric tops with a-type R-branch lines, appearing to form regularly spaced bands of R-branch transitions at $B+C$ intervals. After completing a wide frequency scan, it became possible to assign the rotational spectra of three different rotamers of α -D-glucopyranose labelled as A_α , B_α and C_α . Figure 2 shows a small section of the recorded spectra showing individual transitions of the detected rotamers. They can be independently studied in the supersonic expansion by their rotational spectra, just as in the case of a mixture of stable species. Following an iterative process of fitting and prediction, new assignments for μ_b -type and μ_c -type R-branch spectra for rotamer A_α but only μ_b -type spectra for B_α and C_α rotamers were completed. After discarding the spectra of the observed rotamers, a new set of μ_b -type R-branch transitions, belonging to another rotamer D_α , was

discovered. A rigid rotor model was sufficient to fit²⁶ the measured frequencies given in the Supplementary Information (Table S1) with residuals smaller than the estimated accuracy of frequency measurements. The obtained spectroscopic constants are collected in Table 3.

The analysis of the experimental inertial data alone provided the first piece of evidence about the shape of α -D-glucopyranose rotamers. In this molecule the anomeric OH group is always in axial position and for the predicted most stable conformers the OH groups bonded to C₂, C₃ or C₄ atoms are in equatorial position (see Figure 1c). Since the *ab* inertial plane lies close to the pyranose ring atoms, the planar moment $P_{cc} = \frac{1}{2} (I_c - I_a - I_b) = \sum m_i c_i^2$, given the mass extension out of the *ab* inertial plane, could allow distinction between the axial and equatorial arrangement of the oxygen atom of the hydroxymethyl, -CH₂OH, group. Thus, it has been calculated that rotamers A _{α} and D _{α} have P_{cc} planar moments of 82.77 m_uÅ² and 76.52 m_uÅ², while rotamers B _{α} and C _{α} have similar values of 49.15 m_uÅ² and 51.83 m_uÅ², clearly indicating that the oxygen atom of the hydroxymethyl group is axial to the pyranose ring in conformers A _{α} and D _{α} , while in conformers B _{α} and C _{α} , it assumes an equatorial orientation. Ascription now becomes possible: rotamers A _{α} and D _{α} can be ascribed to the conformers, G-g+/cc/t and G-g+/cl/g-, while rotamers B _{α} and C _{α} could be either G+g-/cc/g+ or the *T*- type conformers of Table 1.

Conformers G-g+/cc/t and G-g+/cl/g- differ only in opposite arrangements of the OH groups; their absolute values of the rotational constants do not allow discriminating between them. However, changing the orientation of the OH groups (from counterclockwise in G-g+/cc/g+, towards clockwise in G-g+/cl/g-) induces small changes in the values of rotational constants of both conformers. Hence, the predicted changes in rotational constants $\Delta A = -17$ MHz, $\Delta B = -3$ MHz, and $\Delta C = 6$ MHz are consistent with those $\Delta A = -14.3$ MHz, $\Delta B = -1.84$ MHz, and $\Delta C = 4.28$ MHz derived from the experimental values of Table 3, thus allowing a conclusive identification of rotamer A _{α} to G-g+/cc/t and rotamer D _{α} to G-g+/cl/g-. Notice that rotational spectroscopy is able to track these subtle structural changes not accessible for other

spectroscopic techniques. In addition, the different arrangements in the orientation of OH groups, *cc* and *cl*, give rise to dramatic changes in the values of the dipole moment components and consequently, in the type of the observed transitions, which can serve as an additional support, confirming the conformational assignment. Taking this into account, the observation of only μ_b -type transitions in the rotamer D_α spectra is consistent with the near-zero values of the electric dipole moment components μ_a and μ_c for conformer *G-g+/cl/t*, whereas the observation of c-type transitions in rotamer A_α spectra is also consistent with a predicted value of $|\mu_c| = 1.3$ D for conformer *G-g+/cc/t*.

The identification of B_α and C_α rotamers as conformers *G+g-/cc/t* and *Tg+/cc/t*, respectively, has been based on the excellent agreement between the *ab initio* and experimental rotational constants in Tables 1 and 3. The observation of μ_a and μ_b -type spectra and the lack of observation of μ_c -type spectra for both B_α and C_α rotamers is only consistent with the predicted electric dipole moment components for conformers *G+g-/cc/t* and *Tg+/cc/t*, further supporting the identification. Scale factors ranging from 1.002 up to 1.007 brings the *ab initio* values of the rotational constants for the *G-g+/cc/t*, *G+g-/cc/t*, *Tg+/cc/t* and *G-g+/cl/g-* conformers nearly into coincidence with the experimental values for rotamers A_α , B_α , C_α and D_α , respectively. This fact clearly shows the global consistency of the conformational assignment. Further searches using predicted rotational constants, corrected by the above scale factors, for the remaining higher-energy conformers *Tt/cl/g-* and *Tg-/cl/g-* in Table 1, failed to observe any spectroscopic signatures belonging to these conformers.

Taking into account all above, the *ab initio* structures (see Table S3 of Supporting Information) can be taken as a good description of the actual structures of the α -D-glucopyranose conformers depicted in Figure 3. Their relative abundances in the supersonic jet have been estimated by intensity measurements of selected rotational transitions.²⁷ These are proportional to its number density in the jet and the corresponding electric dipole moment taken

from the *ab initio* values listed in Table 1. Relative populations of G-g+/cc/g+ : G+g-/cc/g+ : Tg+/cc/g+ : G-g+/cl/g- = 1:0.9(2):0.5(1):0.4(2) are in reasonable agreement with those calculated from the Gibbs free energies in Table 1 of 1:0.90:0.30:0.26. Gauche ⁴C₁ glucopyranose forms with a counter clockwise arrangement of OH groups dominate the conformational panorama of α -D-glucose.

Rotational Spectrum of β -D-glucopyranose

In β -D-glucopyranose, the anomeric hydroxyl group adopts an equatorial configuration, so, all OH groups bonded to the ring atoms are in equatorial position. This change with respect to α -D-glucopyranose should be reflected in a different mass distribution along the principal inertial axes of the molecule. The predicted low-energy conformers of β -D-glucopyranose in Table 2 present sizeable values of the μ_a dipole moment component. Then, we searched first for the most intense μ_a -type R-branch transitions with low K₋₁ values. Wide frequency scans soon revealed the presence of three rotamers, which were initially labelled as A β , B β and C β . μ_a -, μ_b - and μ_c -type transitions were measured for rotamer A β , while μ_a - and μ_b -type were collected for rotamer B β . Only μ_a -type lines were observed for rotamer C β . The spectroscopic constants listed in Table 4 were derived from a rigid rotor analysis of the measured transitions (see Table S2 of the Supporting Information).

As for α -D-glucopyranose conformers, the P_{cc} planar moment can be used to establish the axial or equatorial position of the oxygen atom of the hydroxymethyl group of β -D-glucopyranose. Planar moments of 51.55 m_uÅ² for the A β rotamer and 22.75 m_uÅ² and 23.96 m_uÅ² for B β and C β , respectively, allow us to locate the oxygen atom of the hydroxymethyl group in axial configuration for A β rotamer (*G*- type conformer) and in its equatorial configuration for B β rotamer (*G*+ type). The comparison of the experimental rotational constants (see Table 4) with those calculated *ab initio* (see Table 2) allows a definitive

identification, ascribing rotamer A_β as being $G-g+/cc/t$, B_β as being $G+g-/cc/t$ and C_β as being $Tg+/cc/t$. The types of observed spectra are in accordance with *ab initio* dipole moment components. Scale factors ranging from 1.002 to 1.005 bringing the *ab initio* values of the rotational constants into coincidence with the experimental ones reflect the excellent match between theory and experiment (better than 0.6 %). Hence, the *ab initio* structures (see Table S4 of Supporting Information) can be taken as a good approximation of the actual structures of the three β glucopyranose conformers depicted in Figure 4. Their relative abundances $G-g+/cc/t$: $G+g-/cc/t$: $Tg+/cc/t$ = 0.9(2):1:0.2(1) obtained by relative intensity measurements²⁷ are in good agreement with those 1:0.90:0.20 derived from the calculated Gibbs free energies of Table 2. Following the same procedure used in α -glucopyranose, no spectral signatures attributable to other low-energy conformers of β -D-glucopyranose were observed.

Additional spectroscopic searches were conducted with α and β -D-glucose samples. No traces of the identified α -glucopyranose conformers (see Table 3 and Figure 3) were found in the rotational spectrum of β -D-glucose. Either, no spectral signatures of β -D-glucopyranose conformers (see Table 4 and Figure 4) were found in the rotational spectrum of α -D-glucose. This is a strong indication that the rotational spectrum of laser ablated crystalline samples of α and β -D-glucose reflect the α or β -D-glucopyranose forms found in the X-ray crystalline studies⁶ and that no interconversion between α and β anomers occurs during the laser ablation experiment. This phenomenon takes place through a mutarotation reaction, which is a solvent mediated process, which would not occur that easily especially if the sample is completely dry.²⁸

Discussion

The relative stability among the different conformers of both α and β -glucopyranose (Figure 3 and 4) can be rationalized in terms of different contributing factors. These mainly include stereoelectronic effects (gauche and anomeric effects) and intramolecular hydrogen bonding between vicinal OH groups. The *gauche* effect⁷ is associated to the stabilization of the synclinal (gauche) conformation of two vicinal electronegative groups bonded to a two carbon unit, eg. HO–C–C–OH. In all the observed conformers of α - and β -glucopyranose, all the adjacent OH groups bonded to the ring carbon atoms adopt a gauche or synclinal configuration.

As mentioned above, crystalline samples of α and β -D-glucose do not generate gas phase equilibrium mixture of α and β -D-glucopyranose forms. Although in vacuo *ab initio* calculations predict α -G-g+/cc/t conformer 432 cm⁻¹ being more stable than the β -G-g+/cc/t one,¹² there is no experimental way to test these predictions. Hence, results reported here for α or β anomeric forms could only be discussed separately.

The four observed conformers of α -glucopyranose, depicted in Figure 3, are stabilized by anomeric effect; they have a ⁴C₁ ring configuration with the anomeric OH group towards the axial position. The hydroxyl groups located at equatorial positions are able to form chains of hydrogen bonds, strongly reinforced by sigma-hydrogen bond cooperativity. This phenomenon is associated to chains or cycles of hydrogen bonds between groups that act simultaneously as proton donors and acceptors. The most abundant α conformers, G-g+/cc/t and G+g-/cc/t, present a counterclockwise arrangement of the OH groups with a chain of four cooperative hydrogen bonds O₄H...O₃H...O₂H...O₁H...O₅ and additional O₆H...O₅ interaction with G- or G+ configuration of hydroxymethyl side chain, respectively. The least abundant G-g+/cl/g- conformer presents a clockwise arrangement of three cooperative hydrogen bonds O₁H...O₂H...O₃H...O₄H and one non-cooperative O₆H...O₅. The O₁H...O₅ interaction does not take place in the clockwise oriented network explaining its low abundance. The two most abundant β conformers G-g+/cc/t and β -G+g-/cc/t shown in Figure 4, exhibit the same

conformational shape than that observed in α forms with the obvious differences in the anomeric OH group.

The observation of conformers with an anti orientation of the dihedral angle ($O_6-C_6-C_5-O_5$) constitutes a remarkable fact. Numerous experimental studies on α and β glucopyranosides, both in solid⁶ and solution phases,³⁰ have shown that the dihedral angle ($O_6-C_6-C_5-O_5$) displays a preference for G- and G+ gauche configurations, which has been attributed to the gauche effect.⁷ This feature was exemplified in a statistical analysis of X-ray structures of glucopyranosyl derivatives,²⁹ yielding a rotamer population of 40:0:60 (G+/ T/ G). In contrast to previous results, our gas-phase experiment revealed the existence of *trans* configurations in α -Tg+/cc/t and β -Tg+/cc/t conformers. In agreement with *ab initio* calculations, these forms have a higher energy and are less abundant in the jet. Both conformers exhibit a chain of five cooperative hydrogen bonds $O_6H\cdots O_4H\cdots O_3H\cdots O_2H\cdots O_1H\cdots O_5$ oriented counterclockwise involving the hydroxymethyl group. Therefore, the structure and relative stability of isolated α and β -D-glucopyranose are different from their counterparts in condensed phases.

Conclusion

The present study provides the first experimental information on D-glucose in the gas phase which has led to determine its intrinsic conformational landscape. Four rotamers have been detected for α -glucopyranose and three for β -glucopyranose for which the rotational parameters and relative abundances have been determined. The data provided by LA-MB-FTMW spectroscopy and the fact that they are directly comparable with those of high level *ab initio* computations constitute an unmatched tool to achieve the unambiguous identification of the conformers observed. The glucose conformers are stabilized by the interplay of stereoelectronic hyperconjugative forces, like those associated to anomeric or gauche effects, and the cooperative $OH\cdots O$ chains extended along the entire molecule. The most stable conformers for α -glucopyranose and β - glucopyranose have practically the same configurations

and relative energies, with the exception of the orientation axial (α) or equatorial (β) configuration of the anomeric OH group. This significant change, however, is sufficient to give different physical properties for both species.

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Supporting Information Available

Measured transitions and complete ref 25. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Table 1. Molecular properties predicted *ab initio*^a for the most stable conformers (below 600 cm⁻¹) of α -D-glucopyranose.

Parameter	G-g+/cc/t	G+g-/cc/t	Tg+/cc/t	G-g+/cl/g-	Tt/cl/g-	Tg-/cl/g-
A ^b /MHz	1280	1309	1400	1297	1407	1403
B/MHz	785	766	741	788	751	747
C/MHz	580	533	538	574	544	542
P _{cc} ^c /mÅ ²	84	49	52	75	52	52
μ_a ^d / D	2.0	1.9	2.7	0.0	2.4	1.1
μ_b / D	2.9	2.1	1.0	1.3	0.3	0.1
μ_c / D	1.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.3	0.5
ΔE^e /cm ⁻¹	0	56	151	291	471	550
ΔG^f /cm ⁻¹	0	41	236	200	471	543

^a *Ab initio* calculations (MP2-6-311++G(d,p)). ^b A, B and C are the rotational constants. ^c Planar inertial moment $P_{cc} = 0.5(I_b + I_c - I_a) = \sum_i m_i c_i^2$, where the sum is extended to all atoms, m_i is the mass of atom i and c_i is its corresponding principal inertial axis c coordinate. Conversion factor: 505379.1 uÅ². ^d μ_a , μ_b and μ_c are the electric dipole moment components (1 D = 3.3356×10⁻³⁰ C m). ^e Relative electronic energies calculated at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) electronic energies. ^f Gibbs energies calculated at 298 K.

Table 2. Molecular properties predicted *ab initio*^a for the most stable conformers (below 600 cm⁻¹) of β -D-glucopyranose.

Parameter	G-g+/cc/t	G+g-/cc/t	Tg+/cc/t	G+g-/cc/g-	G-g+/cc/g-	Tg+/cc/g-
A ^b /MHz	1180	1180	1322	1171	1173	1312
B/MHz	820	793	736	796	821	738
C/MHz	536	495	496	496	535	495
P _{cc} ^c /mÅ ²	51	22	25	24	51	24
μ_a ^d / D	2.4	2.4	2.9	2.9	2.1	2.9
μ_b / D	2.0	1.7	0.3	0.6	1.0	1.0
μ_c / D	1.8	0.2	0.2	1.5	0.1	1.5
ΔE^e /cm ⁻¹	0	54	191	332	398	561
ΔG^f /cm ⁻¹	0	41	279	367	412	662

^a *Ab initio* calculations (MP2-6-311++G(d,p)). ^b A, B and C are the rotational constants. ^c Planar inertial moment $P_{cc} = 0.5(I_b + I_c - I_a) = \sum_i m_i c_i^2$, where the sum is extended to all atoms, m_i is the mass of atom i and c_i is its corresponding principal inertial axis c coordinate. Conversion factor: 505379.1 uÅ². ^d μ_a , μ_b and μ_c are the electric dipole moment components (1 D = 3.3356×10⁻³⁰ C m). ^e Relative electronic energies calculated at MP2/6-311++G(d,p) electronic energies. ^f Gibbs energies calculated at 298 K.

Table 3. Experimental spectroscopic constants for the observed rotamers of α -D-glucopyranose.

	Rotamer A α G-g+/cc/t	Rotamer B α G+g-/cc/t	Rotamer C α Tg+/cc/t	Rotamer D α G-g+/cl/g-
A ^a / MHz	1273.49337(38) ^f	1301.13397(41)	1391.1623(14)	1287.82983 (97)
B / MHz	782.494081(16)	763.53994(12)	739.40432(16)	784.3316 (12)
C / MHz	576.147286(95)	530.860574(65)	535.053717(87)	571.86739 (24)
P _{cc} ^b /m _u Å ²	82.76575(13)	49.15210(12)	51.83271(33)	76.51795(72)
$ \mu_a $ / D	Observed ^c	Observed	Observed	
$ \mu_b $ / D	Observed	Observed	Observed	Observed
$ \mu_c $ / D	Observed			
N ^d	31	25	21	5
σ ^e /kHz	2.9	1.9	2.0	2.6

^a A, B and C are the rotational constants. ^b Planar inertial moment $P_{cc} = 0.5(I_b + I_c - I_a) = \sum_i m_i c_i^2$, where the sum is extended to all atoms, m_i is the mass of atom i and c_i is its corresponding principal inertial axis c coordinate. Conversion factor: 505379.1 uÅ². ^c Observation of a-, b-, and c-type transitions for each structure. ^d Number of measured transitions. ^e rms deviation of the fit. ^f Standard errors are shown in parentheses in units of the last digit.

Table 4. Experimental spectroscopic constants for the observed rotamers of β -D-glucopyranose.

	Rotamer A β G-g+/cc/t	Rotamer B β G+g-/cc/t	Rotamer C β Tg+/cc/t
A ^a / MHz	1174.93219(40) ^f	1177.52528(24)	1317.5298(27)
B / MHz	817.04723(15)	789.387699(93)	734.46825(17)
C / MHz	534.474919(97)	493.577635(55)	493.65157(15)
P _{cc} ^b /m _u Å ²	51.55807(21)	22.74701(13)	23.95625(63)
$ \mu_a $ / D	Observed ^c	Observed	Observed
$ \mu_b $ / D	Observed	Observed	
$ \mu_c $ / D	Observed		
N ^d	33	29	16
σ ^e /kHz	3.1	1.7	2.1

^a A, B and C are the rotational constants. ^b Planar inertial moment $P_{cc} = 0.5(I_b + I_c - I_a) = \sum_i m_i c_i^2$, where the sum is extended to all atoms, m_i is the mass of atom i and c_i is its corresponding principal inertial axis c coordinate. Conversion factor: 505379.1 uÅ². ^c Observation of a-, b-, and c-type transitions for each structure. ^d Number of measured transitions. ^e rms deviation of the fit. ^f Standard errors are shown in parentheses in units of the last digit.

Figure 1. (a) Fisher projection of D-glucose. (b) Haworth projections of α and β anomers. (c) ⁴C₁ chair conformations. (d) Newman projections of the plausible conformations of the hydroxymethyl group around C₅-C₆ and C₆-O₆ bonds.

Figure 2. A section of the LA-MB-FTMW spectrum of α -D-glucopyranose showing the rotational transitions for three of the four observed rotamers.

Figure 3. The four observed conformers of α -D-glucopyranose showing the intramolecular hydrogen bond distances in Å.

Figure 4. The three observed conformers of β -D-glucopyranose showing the intramolecular hydrogen bond distances in Å.

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